

Soil and crop management

A quick method of evaluating straw decomposition in flooded soil

Taufiqul Aziz and I. Watanabe, Soil Microbiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Rice straw has an important role in maintaining soil fertility. When incorporated into the soil, rice straw stimulates microbial activity. Its role in increasing soil fertility is dependent on the rate of its decomposition in the field. This work was undertaken to study the rate of rice straw decomposition in the field.

Air-dried rice straw was cut into 2- to 3-cm pieces. One gram was put into 5- × 7-cm bag made of nylon net with a 0.7-mm opening. The bags were placed in 10-cm depth of soil in the rice field at IRRI in September, and then were taken out at 20, 40, 60, and 80 days after incubation. The straw from each bag was gently rinsed once in distilled

Changes in rice straw during its decomposition in the soil. ^a

	0	Day 20	Day 40	Day 60	Day 80
Wt of straw per bag (g)	1.00	0.69 ± 0.04	0.54 ± 0.036	0.50 ± 0.05	0.39 ± 0.05
Ash per bag (g)	0.18	0.22 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.037	0.22 ± 0.036	0.19 ± 0.05
Organic matter per bag (g)	0.82	0.46 ± 0.018	0.33 ± 0.019	0.28 ± 0.027	0.21 ± 0.012
Decrease in organic matter/bag (g)		0.36	0.49	0.55	0.61
Total N (%)	0.47	0.60 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.058	1.03 ± 0.07	1.12 ± 0.13
Increase in N %		0.13	0.36	0.56	0.65

^a Mean and standard deviation (5 replications).

water and the dry weight, ash, and total N% were measured to study the decomposition pattern (see table). Organic matter was determined by ignition loss.

Dry weight and the organic matter of straw per bag decreased rapidly up to 40 days, and then decomposition slowed

down. There was a 46% reduction in dry weight and 60% in organic matter of straw per bag during the 40-day period. The ash content of straw/bag remained more or less the same throughout the period. The total N% of straw increased rapidly up to 60 days (see table). ■

A simple method for middle-term preservation of azolla germplasm

Bai Ke-zhi, Nilda S. Beria, and I. Watanabe, Soil Microbiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Thirty-two strains of azolla including all species except *A. nilotica* and *A. microphylla* have been collected at IRRI. Proper maintenance of this germplasm is a problem. A method was developed to preserve the germplasm for 100 days or more without reinoculation.

The healthy fronds of azolla, grown in the greenhouse or in the field, are washed with tap water. About 100 shoot tips (each with several young leaves) are cut from the fronds and enclosed in small nylon bags. The shoot tips are treated with 2% sodium hypochlorite and 0.1% Polysorbate solution to eliminate algae and other pests epiphytic on the shoot tips. After 2-3 minutes in the solution, the shoot tips are washed sev-

eral times with sterilized distilled water. About 10 shoot tips are placed in 50-ml Erlenmeyer flasks with cotton plugs, each containing 20 ml sterilized nitrogen-free nutrient medium (Holst medium). The inoculations are cultivated in 25°/21°C (12 hours day, 12 hours night) under 12 klux light intensity and 75% relative humidity. Normal fronds are formed from the shoot tips in 2-3 weeks. These clones, which are free from epiphytic algae and other pests, are transferred to 15° / 15°C (12 hours day/ 12 hours night) under about 1 klux fluorescent light for preservation.

Healthy fronds are repropagated from the preserved clones. Preserved material transferred to suitable growth conditions after 100 days are a normal green and retain nitrogen-fixing activity.

An *Anabaena-azollae-free* clone of *A. pinnata* (Tancheng strain) obtained from the Botany Institute of the Chinese Academy of Sciences was also preserved and has remained viable. ■

Effect of presowing moisture regimes and farmyard manure on the forms of iron and manganese in soils and on yield of rice

C. B. Gore and K. R. Sonar, Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science Department, Mahatma Phule Agricultural University, Rahuri 413 722, Maharashtra, India

A greenhouse experiment on calcareous (pH 8.4, organic carbon 0.5%, and CaCO₃ 7.2%) and noncalcareous (pH 8.2, organic carbon 0.62%, and CaCO₃ 1.0%) Vertisols (Vertic Ustropepts) during the 1980 summer studied the effect of adding farmyard manure (0 and 0.75%) and of moisture regimes (dry, saturated, and 3-cm submergence) 15 days before sowing, on the forms of iron (Fe) and manganese (Mn) in soils and on the yield of rice cultivar Tul-japur 1.

Exchangeable Fe and Mn in both soils increased with an increase in pre-

Treatment ^b	Iron content (ppm)				Manganese content (ppm)				Rice yield (g/pot, 6 plants)	
	NH ₄ OAc, pH 4.8		NH ₄ OAc, pH 3.0		Exch. Mn NH ₄ OAc, pH 7		Reducible Mn NH ₄ OAc, pH 7 + 0.2% hydroquinone		Grain	Straw
	8d	15 d	8d	15 d	8d	15 d	8d	15 d		
Cal, FYM, Dry	2.5	2.5	4.1	4.1	1.0	1.0	290	290	7.65	36.80
Cal, FYM, Sat	5.7	7.5	7.4	19.6	7.0	10.5	277	270	12.25	47.60
Cal, FYM, Subm	7.0	9.2	24.7	36.5	9.5	15.0	266	252	19.47	56.00
Cal, no FYM, Dry	2.5	2.5	4.1	4.1	1.0	1.0	290	290	3.85	33.30
Cal, no FYM, Sat	3.7	6.0	7.9	13.6	3.2	7.7	282	277	8.93	44.60
Cal, no FYM, Subm	6.2	8.0	21.4	25.2	4.7	12.1	277	257	16.42	50.60
Noncal, FYM, Dry	4.0	4.0	5.9	5.9	1.8	1.8	312	312	8.15	38.20
Noncal, FYM, Sat	6.2	10.2	19.3	21.2	9.5	14.5	297	287	15.00	47.40
Noncal, FYM, Subm	7.2	10.3	46.9	52.0	13.0	19.0	287	277	20.90	59.40
Noncal, no FYM, Dry	4.0	4.0	5.9	5.9	1.8	1.8	312	312	7.12	37.40
Noncal, no FYM, Sat	5.0	8.7	17.9	17.9	5.0	10.5	303	285	9.60	41.00
Noncal, no FYM, Subm	7.0	9.5	26.7	36.0	8.1	15.5	292	280	15.85	48.90

^a Mean of 2 replications. ^b Cal= calcareous, FYM = farmyard manure, Sat = saturated, Subm = submerged.

sowing moisture from dry to submergence, and with the duration of moisture treatment (see table). Soil saturation and submergence 15 days before sowing resulted in a greater release of exchangeable Fe and Mn, which might be due to reduced conditions (Eh reduced from 530 to 260 mV in calcareous soil and from 510 to 256 mV in noncalcareous soil) and decrease in pH (from 8.2 to 7.6 in calcareous soil and from 8.1 to 7.8 in noncalcareous soil). Noncalcareous soil

recorded higher exchangeable Fe and Mn than calcareous soil. The addition of farmyard manure resulted in higher content of exchangeable Fe and Mn. The highest exchangeable Fe and Mn were observed under the presowing soil submergence treatment with farmyard manure.

Easily reducible Mn, however, showed a reverse trend. It rapidly decreased as a result of presowing moisture regimes with the addition of farm-

yard manure, which was accompanied by an increase in exchangeable Mn.

An increase in rice grain and straw yield was observed. It probably was due to an increase in the supply of Fe and Mn in the soil as a result of soil water treatments 15 days before sowing. The highest grain and straw yield was obtained in noncalcareous soil under presowing submergence treatment with addition of farmyard manure. ■

Population of the weed *Marsilia quartrifoliata* in plots with azolla

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Aduthurai, India

Irrigation water is usually released from Mattur reservoir in June in Thanjavur district. The first short-duration crop in the double-crop wetland system is planted in June-July. In the single-cropped wetland area, long-duration varieties are planted in September-October, 2-3 months after water is released. Submergence of those fields during that period encourages some wetland weeds such as *Marsilia quartrifoliata*, *Panicum repens*, *P. colonum*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Pistia striotus*, and *Echinochloa colona*. *M. quartrifoliata* spreads quickly and manual labor to remove it from the field before planting costs US\$41-103/ha.

At PES, fields where azolla was growing differed in *Marsilia* weed population from fields with no azolla. Weed population was assessed in 10 randomly selected areas, 10 m² each, in which azolla grew densely and in which azolla was absent. The weights follow:

Plots	Mean fresh weed wt (kg/10 m ²)
With dense azolla growth	0.52
Control (no azolla)	26.31

Trials on seed requirements showed that a minimum of 1 t seed material/ha was needed for the samba fields. Azolla can be grown without phosphorus application if the old water is drained from the field once a week and fresh water is maintained at 5-10 cm.

Thus a thick layer of azolla can ward off *M. quartrifoliata* while saving 25 kg N/ha, as previously reported. ■

Azolla manuring rectifies zinc deficiency

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, India

Zinc deficiency is a problem in the second crop (thaladi) immediately following the first crop (kuruvai) in double-cropped wetlands in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu.

A trial with three replications during the 1979-80 thaladi season studied the maximum level of azolla (*A. pinnata*) application that gave a significant additional yield in the variety ADT31. The number of leaves and the intensity of leaf area affected by zinc deficiency were assessed 4 times — 20th, 25th, 30th, and 35th day after transplanting (DT) — as the zinc deficiency was observed in a severe form in the early stages of crop growth. The mean of the maximum